

Quality Education and 21st Century Skills: An Imperative for Inclusive Sustainable Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper addressed the need for education managers and policy implementers to adapt Nigeria's education policies and curriculum in line with 21st century essential skills to cope with technology integration, adaptation as catalyst for 21st century sustainable development. The challenges of educating and learning in the twenty first century Nigeria as discussed in this study are enormous. The geometric progression in the aspects of information and its varying nature are bringing up examinations of the models and the authority of traditional bodies of knowledge managed by educational institutions. In response to the urgency for preparing our students to be knowledgeable in the job opportunities of the future and dynamics of interactions in the society, this paper suggested that the stakeholders in education need to look closely at adapting all- inclusive 21st century learning curricula and drive change through proper funding and building teachers' capacity to demonstrate 21st century skills in support of students' learning amongst others.

Keywords: Quality education, sustainable development, 21st century skills, curriculum and counselling

Introduction

Education in the modern world is a systematic process of acquiring knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes through formal institutions, such as schools, colleges, or universities, as well as informal settings, such as online learning platforms or vocational training centres. It encompasses various subjects and disciplines that aim to broaden individuals' intellectual, personal, social, and economic development. According to UNESCO (2021) education is the process of facilitating learning or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs and habits. Quality education specifically entails issues such as appropriate skill development, gender parity, provision of relevant school infrastructure, equipment, educational materials and resources, scholarships or teaching force. A good quality education according to Flemish Association for Development Cooperation and Technical Assistance (VVOB) (2022) is one that provides all learners with capabilities they require to become economically productive, develop sustainable livelihoods, contribute to peaceful and democratic societies and enhance individual wellbeing. VVOB (2022) stressed further that the learning outcomes of the education cycle must include threshold levels of literacy and numeracy, basic scientific knowledge and life skills including awareness and prevention of diseases.

Education, being a social institution serving the needs of society, is crucial for society to survive and thrive. It should not be only inclusive and supportable, but need to always evolve to meet the challenges of the fast-changing and unpredictable globalized world (Lohna, 2019; Okoorosaye-Orubite, 2019; Abubakar, 2020; Nwosu, 2020; Ogbonnoya, 2020). The Nigeria's National Policy on Education, 6th edition, affirms that education is, among other things, a right of every Nigerian and is to be qualitative, comprehensive, functional and relevant to the needs of the society (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013, p.2). Furthermore, one of the aspects of the Nigerian Objectives of Education stated that 'education is meant for the acquisition of appropriate skills and competencies as equipment for the individual to live in and contribute to the development of the society'. Therefore, to prepare students for handling the complexity of modern societies, policy documents and educational reforms around the globe call for 21st century skills (Kennedy & Sundberg, 2020). Abubakar (2020) posited that the educational policy makers nowadays are shifting from designing and prioritizing high level literacy education towards emphasizing on skills training to promote workforce and economic growth of a nation. Abubakar (2020) stressed that introducing educational system of new approaches that addresses cultural success and promote economic competitiveness, is a prerequisite to every national education.

Chalkiadaki (2018, p.5) defined 21st Century Skills as encompassing a broad range of skill sets and professional attributes, including: creativity, divergent thinking, critical thinking, team working (especially in heterogeneous groups), work autonomy, developed cognitive and interpersonal skills, social and civic competences, responsible national and global citizenship, consciousness of interdependence, acceptance and understanding of diversity, recognition and development of personal attributes, interactive use of tools, communication in mother tongue and foreign languages, mathematical and science competence, digital competence, sense of initiative and entrepreneurship, accountability, leadership, cultural awareness and expression, physical well-being. Babalola (2020) argued that effective acquisition of these skills in the school is predicated on adequate provision of technological resources, adequate school infrastructure and continuous professional development of teachers for innovative instructional delivery. This implies that students, who will come of age in the 21st century, need to be taught different skills than those

learned by students in the 20th century, and that the skills they learn should reflect the specific demands that will be placed upon them in a complex, competitive, knowledge-based, information- age, technology-driven economy and society.

In Nigeria, qualitative education remains the only means of releasing the general population from the overwhelming effect of the escalating poverty, social injustice, economic meltdown, malnutrition, insecurity and all such social vices confronting the Nigerian economy (Birabil & Ogeh, 2020, Akor & Amadioha, 2020; Ogbonnaya, 2020). This implies that education remains the most effective index for transformation of the society as well as the actualization of the desire and aspirations of the people. Nevertheless, with Nigeria falling behind in preparing its young people for the workplace of the future, it is therefore expedient on the part of all stakeholders that an effective and sustainable reforms in the national curriculum should be put in place with priorities given to twenty first century skills which can usher students into the emerging era and prepare them for jobs of the future.

Theoretical Framework

This study adapts the Framework for 21st Century Learning model as theoretical framework for its discussion.

The Framework for 21st Century Learning

This popular framework was designed by the Partnership for 21st Century Skills (P21) (2009). It describes the skills, knowledge, and expertise students must master to succeed in work and life. The framework combines content knowledge, specific skills, expertise, and literacies. P21 believes that the base of 21st century learning is the acquisition of key academic subject knowledge, and that schools must build on that base with additional skills including learning skills, life skills, and literacy skills. This framework is based on the assertion that twenty-first-century challenges will demand a broad skill set emphasizing core subject skills, social and cross-cultural skills, proficiency in languages other than English, and an understanding of the economic and political forces that affect societies.

Making the shift to support these learning approaches requires structural, social, and cultural change in Nigeria's education policies at all levels. This shift requires innovative thinking, monetary commitment, and deliberate action on the part of government at all levels and non- government organizations and professional educators. Additionally, major government agencies and non-government organizations must partner with the teachers, local community stakeholders, and school board members, each having their own unique viewpoints and wide-ranging tolerances for change.

Developing Responsive 21st Century Curriculum for Nigeria Education System

Curriculum is an organized set of formal education or process of training intentions. It is a four-step plan that comprises four phases (purpose, design, implementation and assessment (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). According to UNESCO's International Bureau of Education (IBE-UNESCO) (2015), curriculum articulates educational domains (policy-making, educational planning, curriculum development, teacher education, student learning and assessment amongst others) to give effect to lifelong learning. Therefore,

curriculum development and change should be guided by all-inclusive and universal approach, which is critical to ensuring effectiveness and sustainability, instead of a piecemeal approach. Such change processes should be based on broad consultations, in order to ensure relevance, common understanding, ownership, commitment, and support (Mmantseta, 2019). The key drivers of curricula change in the 21st century as stated by Mmantseta, (2019) are:

- i. The transition to knowledge and technology driven growth that fueled demand for different skills for jobs, work, and life and the need for curricula to reflect these skills if they are to remain relevant.
- ii. The broadening concept of development with concerns for peace, justice, rights, ethics, equity, inclusion, climate, and sustainability have led to curricula for global citizenship education.
- iii. The Sustainable Development Goal 4 emphasizes equity of education quality and lifelong learning for all as key enablers of development.
- iv. The Internet has become a major source of information and knowledge requires skills to not only use ICTs to access information but, more importantly, competence to evaluate the credibility, relevance, and applicability of that information in addressing challenges.
- v. The new demands of work and workplaces in 21st century demand in-depth knowledge of subject matters required for specialized work such as engineering, medicine, plumbing, teaching, soft skills, or 21st century skills to round up their technical knowledge into effective competences.
- vi. Climate change drives the need for education for sustainable development and for the educational grooming of new global citizens with sustainable lifestyles and exemplary environmental custodianship.
- vii. Social fracture and political instability due to injustice, inequity, exclusion, oppression, social fracture, and political instability call for inclusion of culture and humanities in curricula interfaced with technology.
- viii. New ways of working due to globalization and outsourcing services across borders becoming the norm require people competences to collaborate across national and virtual boundaries to share information and emerging knowledge.
- ix. Changes in the nature of tools required in 21st century work places are also stimulating demand for new competences for effective and efficient performance at work.
- x. Need to develop functional curricular for youth who are multiply disengaged from education, work, jobs, families, and communities.
- xi. Heightening recognition of student and teacher agency as co-curricula designers, a role that has mostly been centralized on specialists at ministry headquarters.
- xii. Advances in our understanding of learning.

The United Nations (UN) (2012) stressed the urgent need for teachers to design collaborative and authentic learning activities that develop students' understanding, skills and values with a view to negotiating viable solutions to worldwide socio-economic, political conflicts, environmental challenges and cultural divisions that will undoubtedly continue into the next century. Recognizing that learning is increasingly happening individually beyond formal educational settings, the role of teachers in Nigeria will have to evolve from dispensers of information and knowledge to facilitators and enablers of learning. However, the process of reforming schools and learning does not imply an immediate overhaul of the curriculum or the transformation of schools and classrooms with new technology and organizational schemes. Instead, the first priority is to ascertain what elements should be removed from an already over-burdened Nigerian curriculum

particularly, less relevant knowledge, before pushing in new competencies and skills or transforming the way class time is used.

Quality Education for Sustainable Development

According to SDG-4, quality education is the foundation of sustainable development, and therefore of the Sustainable Development Goals. Every child must be able to access and complete an inclusive, quality pre-primary, primary and secondary education in order to meet the Global Goal for education by 2030. Quality education provides the outcomes which are needed for individuals, communities, and societies to prosper. For education to be qualitative, it must focus not just on the teaching of students, curriculum and how it is being taught (Pedagogy). Key elements of qualitative education according to UNESCO (2016) include:

- i. Safe and supportive learning environment.
- ii. Quality teacher.
- iii. Availability of infrastructure which is crucial to a safe and quality learning environments.
- iv. Adaptive and dynamic curriculum.

Ojukwu (2012) noted that education is incomplete until it satisfies the aim of the person being educated. Despite the efforts of the government, the private sector, and international donors towards addressing the challenges facing education in Nigeria, key obstacles continue to hinder its implementation of SDG-4. These challenges include poor funding in the educational system, inadequate basic infrastructure and educational facilities, inadequate, obsolete and non- application of information communication technology facilities, low quality in our educational programs, poor staff development programs, inadequate teaching staff /poor quality of teaching staff, poor remunerations of the teachers, poor credibility of academic qualifications obtained in Nigerian Universities today, unstable political environment, frequent labor disputes and closures of universities, brain-drain, persistent inequality in access to education on grounds of household wealth disparity in spite of the free Universal Basic Education, omissions in the national policies particularly relating to education quality and learning needs of internally displaced children amongst others. Anekwe, 2020; Babalola, 2020; Aduwa, 2021; Bodand & Lengkat, 2021; Usman & Chinyere; 2021; Centre for the Study of the Economies of Africa (CSEA), 2022).

Edo, David & Uriri (2020) recommended that to be in tandem with the 21st century skills, certain core competencies such as: collaboration, digital literacy, critical thinking, and problem- solving must be appropriately addressed by management of the educational system. This, they stressed is the only process of adhering to dynamic pressures or challenges from the encroachment of advanced technology. Edo, David & Uriri (2020) posited that it is through the attainment of mastery in these areas that education in the 21st century will survive and flourish in the achievement of the predetermination of goals and objectives. Therefore, educators, administrators, researchers, and policy makers are expected to update the concept and practice of teaching and learning, as well as all other aspects of this multifaceted organization in ensuring quality preparation of all students to life and work.

Ogbonnaya (2020) argued that when a nation understands the importance of education as a catalyst to development, such a nation would experience astronomic socioeconomic

growth in a short time. However, according to Ogbonnaya, for a developing country like Nigeria, there is the need to realize how education can be used to improve the economy. This would enable education to assume its position as the key to national development in Nigeria in the 21st century. Through its findings, Centre for the Study of the Economies of Africa (CSEA) (2022) recommended that the following proactive steps be taken for Nigeria to achieve SDG-4.

- Earmarking a significant proportion of the revenue accruing to the education sector. On the policy side, existing policies should be reviewed to integrate SDG4 into all national development plans. Its implementation should be institutionalized at state and local levels.
- Private sector partners should engage with the government to achieve SDG4. They can do so by internalizing sustainable business practices and implementing more strategic corporate social responsibility programs in education.
- Education programs should be prioritized in the development assistance portfolio through reaching out to the International Donor community.

According to CEAS (2020) adopting this multi-stakeholder approach and strategy will enable Nigeria to be better positioned in achieving SDG4 by 2030 and contribute significantly to building an inclusive and sustainable society where every child has access to equitable and quality education.

Raising Foundational Skills Requirements for 21st Century Nigeria

The most recent developments in the knowledge society and the subsequent changes in the world of work at the global level are raising skill/qualification requirements for job entry and subsequently demand for a more knowledgeable and skilled workforce that every learner who goes through basic education will be expected to develop are: critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, communication, information literacy, media literacy, technology literacy, flexibility, leadership, initiative, productivity, social skills (Partnership for 21st Century Skills (P21) (2009; Suresh, 2020). In the modern world, education has evolved to meet the changing needs and demands of society. It goes beyond traditional classroom settings and now incorporates technological advancements and globalized perspectives. Some key aspects of education in the modern world include:

- i. **Access and inclusivity:** Efforts are being made to ensure equal access to education for all individuals, regardless of their socioeconomic background, gender, ethnicity, or physical ability. Initiatives such as online education, scholarships, and inclusive classrooms aim to bridge the education gap and promote diversity.
- ii. **Focus on critical thinking and problem-solving:** Education now emphasizes the development of critical thinking skills and the ability to solve complex problems. Instead of rote memorization, students are encouraged to analyse, question, and evaluate information to make informed decisions.
- iii. **Technology integration:** Technology has revolutionized education by providing innovative learning tools and platforms. Virtual classrooms, online courses, interactive apps, and digital resources enable flexible and personalized learning experiences. It also prepares students to adapt to a technology-driven world.
- iv. **Global perspectives:** With increasing globalization and interconnectedness, education in the modern world encourages global perspectives and intercultural understanding. It

- promotes awareness of diverse cultures, languages, and global issues to foster empathy, collaboration, and a sense of global citizenship.
- v. **Holistic development:** Modern education acknowledges the importance of a holistic approach to learning. It considers not only intellectual development but also focuses on emotional intelligence, social skills, creativity, physical fitness, and ethical values. It aims to prepare individuals for all aspects of life, including work, relationships, and personal growth.
 - vi. **Lifelong learning:** In the rapidly changing world, education is viewed as a lifelong process. It encourages individuals to continuously update their knowledge and skills to adapt to new technologies and evolving job requirements. Lifelong learning opportunities are provided through professional development courses, adult education programs, and online resources.

Implication for Counselling.

Quality education in the 21st century has several implications for counselling in Nigeria.

- i. **Skill development:** In the 21st century, education has shifted from rote memorization to skill development. With a focus on critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, and collaboration, counselling in Nigeria needs to adapt to help students develop these 21st-century skills. Counsellors can incorporate activities and interventions that enhance these skills in their counselling sessions.
- ii. **Technology integration:** Technology is an integral part of education in the 21st century. It provides students with access to a vast array of information and resources. Consequently, counsellors in Nigeria need to familiarize themselves with technology-based counselling platforms, online resources, and digital tools. They can use technology to provide counselling services remotely, access up-to-date information, and collaborate with other professionals.
- iii. **Career guidance:** The 21st century is characterized by rapid technological advancements and globalization. It is essential for counsellors in Nigeria to provide career guidance that is aligned with the demands of the modern workforce. They should offer information about emerging industries, job trends, and equip students with the necessary skills to succeed in a dynamic job market.
- iv. **Mental health support:** The increased pressures and challenges faced by students in the 21st century require comprehensive mental health support. Counsellors need to address issues such as anxiety, stress, cyberbullying, and mental health disorders effectively. They must employ evidence-based interventions and collaborate with other professionals to ensure students' well-being.
- v. **Multicultural awareness:** In the 21st century, cultural diversity is celebrated, and students come from various backgrounds. Counsellors in Nigeria should be culturally competent and sensitive to provide inclusive counselling services. They need to understand the influence of culture on students' lives, respect diversity, and tailor counselling approaches accordingly.
- vi. **Lifelong learning:** The 21st-century education emphasizes lifelong learning. Counsellors in Nigeria should promote a growth mind-set and encourage students to embrace continuous learning. They can provide resources, workshops, and counselling sessions to help students develop a love for learning and adapt to a rapidly changing world.

In conclusion, quality education in the 21st century has several implications for counselling in Nigeria. Counsellors need to adapt to skill development, integrate technology, provide career guidance, support mental health, be culturally aware, and promote lifelong learning. By incorporating these elements into their practice, counsellors can effectively support students in navigating the challenges of the modern world.

Conclusion

Nigeria will therefore needs a total overhauling and restructuring to improve the performance of education at all levels in the country as the nation as the country is confronted with the 21st century and also compete in the global economy, where growth will be based even more heavily on technical and scientific knowledge. The implications of these are that students, particularly in Nigeria who will come of age in the 21st century, need to be taught different skills than those learned by students in the 20th century, and that the skills they learn should reflect the specific demands that will be placed upon them in a complex, competitive, knowledge-based, information-age, technology-driven economy and society. Nigerian government and non- governmental organizations must acknowledge the many reasons why twenty-first century learning must be different. They must critically evaluate education system to determine whether schools are living up to current expectations and ask how successful their schools actually are in equipping learners to compete favorably in a global economy.

Recommendations

Making the shift to 21st Century learning requires government, non-government organizations and educators in Nigeria to adjust instruction, assessment, and professional development to support students' learning. The foregoing discussion implies that:

- i. The Federal and States Ministry of Education, Ministry of Science and Technology, and other relevant ministries, agencies, parastatals, professional bodies, educational and research agencies/bodies in conjunction with Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) need to figure out how to adapt and adopt the 21st century learning to fit the current learning framework through designing new instructional strategies and building teachers capacity to demonstrate 21st century skills in support of student learning.
- ii. Students at all levels should be provided with multiple opportunities to engage in challenging tasks that address 21st Century skills. This type of learning can occur both in out of the classroom using on-line collaborative platform technology. Private sector in Nigeria should key into providing creative and innovative, platforms that will give much emphasis on professional as well as vocational development of the students.
- iii. Proper funding of the new 21st century learning module through a special funding channel like the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TET Fund) should be extended to all levels of education in Nigeria.
- iv. Identifying infrastructural environments that need to be in place in order to create or facilitate the demand for 21st century skills as well as infrastructural capabilities that are required in order to provide those skills.

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